

Polysemy as a linguistic phenomenon

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Abstract: This article is due to polysemy as a linguistic phenomenon. Language is defined as system of communication that uses arbitrary signals such as voice sounds, gestures or written symbols. However, frankly speaking, language is too complex, intriguing, and mysterious to be adequately explained by a brief definition. To carry meaning is the most organic function of the language. Most of the problems in linguistic science are closely intimately bound of semasiology and call for scientific analysis of communication in words. The study of words is not exclusively a study of roots and stems, of prefixes or suffixes. The mysterious world of words is an object of scientific investigation.

Key words: Polysemy, phenomena, communication, transference, morphological, circumstances, lexicology.

Since the times of Plato and Aristotle, the process of development of new meaning in language is the most important and attractive research problem among scholars, philosophers and grammarians. From those times sameness of meaning was difficult to cope with but it was more complicated to distinguish difference of meaning. The position is the same nowadays. Not only there are different meanings in different words; but also it is the fact that the same word may have a set of meanings. This concept is called polysemy. Polysemy is the ability of words to have more than one meaning and the words having several meanings are described by the term polysemantic. The bulk of words in the English and Uzbek languages are polysemantic. One of the most characteristic features of the languages is highly interchangeability. According to this, it should be noted that the treasury of the language's expressive resources largely depends on the growth of polysemy in the language. Generally speaking, some people who are not aware of linguistic argues that a language has drawbacks in words if the need arises for the same word to be applied to several different phenomena. Actually, it is exactly the opposite: if each word is found to be capable of conveying at least two concepts instead of one, the expressive potential of the whole vocabulary increases twofold. Hence, a word's semantic development is a great advantage in a language. On the other hand, it should be mentioned that the range of sound integrations that human speech organs are able to make is limited. Thence, within a certain period of widening new meaning by

morphological means is restricted as well, and polysemy becomes increasingly important for broadening the range of vocabulary. Consequently, it should be clear that the process of enriching the vocabulary does not include entirely in adding new words to it, but also, in the constant development of polysemy. The system of meanings of any polysemantic word increases constantly, mostly through the centuries, as too many new meanings are affixed to old ones, or out some of them. As a result, the complex processes of polysemy progress include both the apparent of new vocabulary and the absence of old ones. Until now, the common aspiration with English and Uzbek vocabulary systems at the current period of their history is to get improved the total number of its meanings and in this way to supply with a quantitative and qualitative growth of the language's expressive resources. New meaning exists in two ways: first is the historical one: different sorts of changes in a nation's social life, in its culture, knowledge, technology, arts cause for appearing the vocabularies which need to be filled. Newly created objects, new concepts and phenomena must be given the name: word forming and borrowing foreign ones. New meanings can also be developed according to linguistic factors - the second cause. Linguistically speaking, the development of new meanings, and also a complete change of meaning, may be caused through the influence of other words, mostly of synonyms.

The process of development of a new meaning termed is traditionally termed transference. Some scholars mistakenly use the term -" transference of meaning" which is a serious mistake. It is very important to that in any case of semantic change it is not the meaning but the word that is being transferred from one term into another (from a horse-drawn vehicle into railway car).The result of such transference is the appearance of new meaning.

Words often sign not of one but of several things. The linguistic mechanism works naturally in many ways to prevent ambiguity and provide the clue to distinguish the necessary meaning. It's also important to take into consideration the significance of the context, linguistic or non-linguistic; many ambiguities are never noticed because the various possible meanings are excluded by the situation. Important observations in this area of the vocabulary have been made by contextual, distributional and transformational analysis.

Another problem of polysemy is the usage of the same word in more distinct meanings in pertinent a great deal of other important questions. These are: the growth of various kinds of synonyms, as a result of semantic transfers of lexical units and homonymy. Describing polysemy as a linguistic development, polysemy was made

difference between two sides by Charles Bally, first, when one linguistic term has several meanings, and the meaning is expressed by several linguistic signs. Words can extend in connotative capacity in accord with the nature with the meanings connected with them. In the ability of connotation maintains the stock strength of language. Without this language would lose much of its meaningfulness and pliability. The frequency of polysemy which is changeable in different languages depending on different circumstances. Languages where origin and formation are sparingly used to have a tendency to fill the gaps in vocabulary by appending new word to existing terms.

Polysemy more often occurs in generic words than in specific terms whose meanings are less subject to variation.

It is very significant not to fail to take into account the fact that few words have simple meanings. Basically most words have, besides their primary meaning, an edge of associated meanings. In actual fact, language exists a great deal of its expressive ability to the ideas and feelings related to words. There are normally different connected meanings which have the appearance in changing levels of prominence determined by the context.

The development of the words which is used in various context and the changes of meaning takes a major interest in contrastive lexicology and typological research of languages.

Conclusion. Some meanings invariably come to the fore when we hear the word in actual speech or see in written. Other meanings make themselves evident only when the word is used in certain context. The context makes the meaning explicit, in other words, brings them out. This is not to say that polysemantic words have meanings only in context. As has already been emphatically stressed the semantic structure of the word is a dialectic entity and involves dialectical permanency and invariability.

Meaning should always be acknowledged as including the connection with language to the rest of the world and such expression plays an essential role in the definition of language.

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